

This is the accepted manuscript (postprint) of the following article:

E. Salahinejad, M. Hadianfard, D. Macdonald, I. Karimi, D. Vashae, L. Tayebi, *Aqueous sol-gel synthesis of zirconium titanate (ZrTiO₄) nanoparticles using chloride precursors*, *Ceramics International*, 38 (2012) 6145-6149.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2012.04.064>

Aqueous sol-gel synthesis of zirconium titanate (ZrTiO₄) nanoparticles using chloride precursors

E. Salahinejad ^{a,b,c}, M.J. Hadianfard ^c, D. Vashae ^d, D.D. Macdonald ^{b,e}, I. Karimi ^c, L. Tayebi ^{a,*}

^a Helmerich Advanced Technology Research Center, School of Materials Science and Engineering, Oklahoma State University, OK 74106, USA

^b Center for Electrochemical Science and Technology, Department of Materials Science and Engineering, Pennsylvania State University, University Park, PA 16802, USA

^c Department of Materials Science and Engineering, School of Engineering, Shiraz University, Zand Blvd., 7134851154, Shiraz, Iran

^d Helmerich Advanced Technology Research Center, School of Electrical and Computer Engineering, Oklahoma State University, OK 74106, USA

^e Center for Research Excellence in Corrosion, King Fahd University of Petroleum and Minerals, Dhahran 31261, Saudi Arabia

Abstract

Zirconium titanate powders were synthesized by a straightforward sol-gel method using zirconium and titanium chlorides as metal precursors, deionized water as solvent and oxygen donor, and a NaOH solution for adjusting pH to 7. According to transmission electron microscopy, amorphous particles of nearly 5 nm in size with a relatively spherical morphology were prepared. Thermogravimetry and differential scanning calorimetry analyses on the xerogel at a heating rate of 10 °C/min indicated a crystallization temperature of 690 °C, which is comparable with previous reports. Furthermore, via differential scanning calorimetry studies using the Kissinger's equation, the activation energy for ZrTiO₄ crystallization was determined to be 850 kJ/mol. Structural evaluations in the isothermal regime, using X-ray diffraction experiments, implied the onset of ZrTiO₄ crystallization at 550 °C.

* Corresponding author: *E-mail address*: lobat.tayebi@okstate.edu (L. Tayebi)

This is the accepted manuscript (postprint) of the following article:

E. Salahinejad, M. Hadianfard, D. Macdonald, I. Karimi, D. Vashaei, L. Tayebi, *Aqueous sol-gel synthesis of zirconium titanate (ZrTiO₄) nanoparticles using chloride precursors*, *Ceramics International*, 38 (2012) 6145-6149.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2012.04.064>

Keywords: Sol-gel processes (A); X-ray methods (B); Thermal properties (C)

1. Introduction

Zirconium titanate (ZrTiO₄) is an attractive ceramic for electronic, optical, chemical, catalytic, and biomedical applications [1–6], but demanding high purity and homogeneity. One of the promising approaches to synthesize homogeneous ceramic powders is the sol-gel process. In this method, when a high level of homogeneity is achieved, the obtained amorphous materials crystallize at temperatures of several hundred degrees lower than in classical routes, such as traditional melting and powder processing [7–11]. In addition, as a result of the development of high specific surface area powders by the sol-gel process, much lower sintering temperatures are required.

The sol-gel preparation of zirconium titanate can be conducted by hydrolysis and condensation of inorganic salts [9,12,13] or alkoxides [14–16] as precursors, where the control of the hydrolysis and condensation processes is essential when establishing procedures especially for the latter. A number of non-hydrolytic sol-gel processes have been also focused on producing zirconium titanate powders [10,11]. On the other hand, nanostructured TiO₂-ZrO₂ powders and thin films have been prepared by an aqueous particulate sol-gel route from titanium isopropoxide and zirconium acetate hydrate as precursors [17]. However, to our knowledge, no work has been reported to date on the aqueous particulate sol-gel synthesis of zirconium titanate from chloride precursors.

In this research, a straightforward aqueous particulate sol-gel method, as an environmentally friendly processing, was used to produce zirconium titanate powders. The

This is the accepted manuscript (postprint) of the following article:

E. Salahinejad, M. Hadianfard, D. Macdonald, I. Karimi, D. Vashae, L. Tayebi, *Aqueous sol-gel synthesis of zirconium titanate (ZrTiO₄) nanoparticles using chloride precursors*, *Ceramics International*, 38 (2012) 6145-6149.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2012.04.064>

process is based on the hydrolysis of metal chlorides, in which alkoxide functions are formed *in situ*. One of the advantages of this route is employing an alternative (chloride precursors) to alkoxide precursors used in polymeric sol-gel methods to develop a product at lower cost, which is a significant attribute. This paper focuses on the sol-gel synthesis and characterization of zirconium titanate starting from ZrCl₄ and TiCl₄ as the metal precursors.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Sample preparation

18.2 mmol of zirconium tetrachloride (ZrCl₄, Alfa Aesar, 99.5 %) was gradually added to 400 mL of deionized water and stirred for 15 min. 18.2 mmol of titanium tetrachloride (TiCl₄, Alfa Aesar, 99.99 %) was added dropwise to the solution and magnetically stirred for 2 h, leading to a solution of 0.98 in pH measured using a calibrated pH meter (Sartorius Professional Meter PP-15). Subsequently, an aqueous solution of NaOH (2 M) was added dropwise under magnetic stirring conditions until the pH value approached 7, forming a white hydrogel. After aging for 30 min, in order to remove chloride ion, the hydrogel was rinsed several times with deionized water, and the absence of chloride ions was checked using AgNO₃. The obtained sample was centrifuged at 6000 rpm for 10 min, washed with ethanol, again centrifuged, and finally dried at 60 °C for 2 h, developing white agglomerated powders (xerogel). The obtained powder was calcined at 500, 550, and 600 °C for 1 h with a heating rate of 10 °C/min in a nitrogen atmosphere.

2.2. Structural and thermal characterization

This is the accepted manuscript (postprint) of the following article:

E. Salahinejad, M. Hadianfard, D. Macdonald, I. Karimi, D. Vashae, L. Tayebi, *Aqueous sol-gel synthesis of zirconium titanate (ZrTiO₄) nanoparticles using chloride precursors*, *Ceramics International*, 38 (2012) 6145-6149.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2012.04.064>

A transmission electron microscope (TEM, JEOL JEM-2100) operating at an acceleration voltage of 200 kV was used to evaluate the powder particle size and morphology. To do so, a small amount of the powder was dispersed in ethanol, ultrasonicated for 15 min, and then dropped on a carbon grid. To study the thermal behavior of the xerogel, simultaneous thermo-gravimetry and differential scanning calorimetry analyses (TGA/DSC, Netzsch, STA 449 F1 Jupiter[®]) were performed under a flowing argon atmosphere in an alumina container. The X-ray diffraction (XRD) pattern of the xerogel and calcined powders was recorded by a Bruker AXS Inco. diffractometer using Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.54056 \text{ \AA}$).

3. Results and discussion

The TEM observations of the xerogel powder particles (before calcination) show two typical features. As depicted in Fig. 1(a), despite dispersion in ethanol and ultrasonication, some agglomerated particles of 50-100 nm in size can be still seen, making it difficult to distinguish the real particle size and morphology. This strong tendency toward agglomeration is due to the significant surface-to-volume ratio and surface tension of nanoparticles. Nonetheless, according to Fig. 1(b), on the edge of the agglomerated particles, powder particles of approximately 5 nm in diameter with a relatively spherical morphology can be recognized. The related selected area diffraction (SAD) pattern (Fig. 1(c)) indicates homogenous featureless diffraction halos attributed to an amorphous structure. No diffraction spots or sharp rings associated with crystalline phases can be observed, suggesting the synthesis of fully amorphous nanoparticles.

The TGA and DSC profiles of the xerogel at a heating rate of 10 °C/min are provided in Fig. 2. In the TGA curve, a pronounced weight loss of 15% is observed from 100 °C to 250

This is the accepted manuscript (postprint) of the following article:

E. Salahinejad, M. Hadianfard, D. Macdonald, I. Karimi, D. Vashae, L. Tayebi, *Aqueous sol-gel synthesis of zirconium titanate (ZrTiO₄) nanoparticles using chloride precursors*, *Ceramics International*, 38 (2012) 6145-6149.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2012.04.064>

°C. A broad endothermic peak at around 120 °C and a sharp exothermic peak at 690 °C are also observed in the DSC curve. Considering both analyses simultaneously, it is evident that the first event, the endothermic one with a considerable weight loss, is due to the removal of residual water and chloride during heating. On the other hand, the second sharp event was accompanied by no weight loss and is attributed to crystallization of the amorphous phase developed by the sol-gel method, as verified by XRD and TEM studies below. In accordance with the DSC profile, the onset crystallization temperature and crystallization peak temperature are 575 and 690 °C, respectively.

To study the kinetic behavior of the crystallization event, further DSC experiments on the xerogel were carried out at different heating rates of 20, 30, 40, and 50 °C/min. Based on the data shown in Fig. 3(a), by increasing the heating rate, the crystallization peak is shifted to higher temperatures since the crystallization process from an amorphous phase is a diffusional and thermally-activated transformation controlled via nucleation and growth. The activation energy for crystallization (E_c) can be determined by the Kissinger's equation [18]:

$$\ln\left(\frac{T_c^2}{C}\right) = \frac{E_c}{RT_c} + \text{const.} \quad (1)$$

where T_c , C , and R are the crystallization peak temperature, heating rate, and universal gas constant respectively. Fig. 3(b) demonstrates the linear relationship between $\ln(T_c^2/C)$ and $(1/T_c)$. From the slope of the curve, the value of E_c can be easily determined to be 850 kJ/mol. It has been reported that the activation energy of ZrTiO₄ crystallization from amorphous powders prepared by sol-gel methods is 620 kJ/mol with the crystallization peak appearing at 642 °C [19] and 139-323 kJ/mol with the peak becoming evident at 530-680 °C [2].

Compared to the results of this work, it can be concluded that the activation energy of ZrTiO₄ crystallization strongly depends on the preparation conditions. The activation energy of

This is the accepted manuscript (postprint) of the following article:

E. Salahinejad, M. Hadianfard, D. Macdonald, I. Karimi, D. Vashae, L. Tayebi, *Aqueous sol-gel synthesis of zirconium titanate (ZrTiO₄) nanoparticles using chloride precursors*, *Ceramics International*, 38 (2012) 6145-6149.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2012.04.064>

crystallization calculated by the Kissinger's equation is the activation energy required for growth [20]. The growth of nuclei needs an atomic rearrangement of the constituents, which is closely related to their diffusivity. Indeed, the difference of the activation energy calculated for this material synthesized by different procedures might be due to differences in the particle size, degree of hydration, homogeneity, and short-range order of the amorphous phase [2].

To assess the structural evolution in the course of heating, particularly in the case of isothermal heat treatment, the XRD analyses were conducted on the xerogel before and after calcination at 500, 550, and 600 °C, as represented in Fig. 4. The broad halo pattern of the xerogel [Fig. 4(a)] suggests a typical amorphous pattern, as confirmed by its SAD pattern [Fig. 1(c)]. As can be observed, the amorphous structure is still stable at 500 °C [Fig. 4(b)]; however, the appearance of a number of ZrTiO₄ reflections in the XRD pattern of the sample calcined at 550 °C, provided in Fig. 4(c), is indicative of the onset of structural ordering and crystallization. Fig. 4(d) specifies the XRD pattern of the powder calcined at 600 °C, inferring the crystalline ZrTiO₄ phase with a crystallite size of 13 nm, determined by the EVA software using the Scherrer equation for the XRD maxima. The instrument broadening was calibrated by using a standard sample. Note that it is reasonable to neglect the strain contribution to broadening at low Bragg angles [21]. The XRD reflections were also confirmed by the ICSD reference code of 00-034-0415 for zirconium titanate with the orthorhombic α -PbO₂ type structure, in which Zr and Ti atoms are in octahedral oxygen coordination. No XRD reflection corresponding to TiO₂ and ZrO₂ can be detected. The direct crystallization of ZrTiO₄ at the low temperature is due to the high level of homogeneity of the xerogel. It has been reported that, in the case of low homogeneity, TiO₂ crystallization occurs before

This is the accepted manuscript (postprint) of the following article:

E. Salahinejad, M. Hadianfard, D. Macdonald, I. Karimi, D. Vashae, L. Tayebi, *Aqueous sol-gel synthesis of zirconium titanate (ZrTiO₄) nanoparticles using chloride precursors*, *Ceramics International*, 38 (2012) 6145-6149.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2012.04.064>

crystallization into ZrTiO₄ [22]. The TEM micrograph and SAD pattern of the sample calcined at 600 °C are illustrated in Fig. 5. Compared to the xerogel (Fig. 1), the powder particles have grown, with the driving force being a reduction in the surface energy, and have approached an average size of 50 nm with a relatively wide size range of 20 nm to 100 nm. Moreover, the high crystallinity of this powder results in distinct Debye-Scherrer diffraction spots in the SAD pattern (Fig. 5(b)).

As shown above, based on the XRD analysis, the crystallization is initiated at 550 °C (even at lower temperatures), but the crystallization peak of the DSC test is located at 690 °C. The difference of the crystallization behavior detected from the DSC and XRD evaluations is due to the difference between the thermal regimes applied. During the DSC analysis, heating is continuous at a rate of 10 °C/min; nonetheless, the XRD patterns were obtained from the samples calcined at the different temperatures for 1 h under isothermal conditions, where time for the diffusional transformation of crystallization is provided, allowing the onset of crystallization at low temperatures.

In conclusion, typical advantages of this processing route described in this paper include: i) It is a straightforward and uncomplicated procedure, ii) It allows for the successful synthesis of ZrTiO₄ nanoparticles with a crystallization temperature much lower than in classical ZrTiO₄ processing methods, and iii) It is capable of producing low cost powders compared to polymeric sol-gel methods using alkoxide precursors.

4. Conclusions

This is the accepted manuscript (postprint) of the following article:

E. Salahinejad, M. Hadianfard, D. Macdonald, I. Karimi, D. Vashae, L. Tayebi, *Aqueous sol-gel synthesis of zirconium titanate (ZrTiO₄) nanoparticles using chloride precursors*, *Ceramics International*, 38 (2012) 6145-6149.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2012.04.064>

In this work, an aqueous sol-gel procedure using zirconium and titanium chlorides was developed to synthesize ZrTiO₄ powder. From this study, the following conclusions could be drawn:

- According to the TEM studies, amorphous particles of almost 5 nm in size with a relatively spherical morphology were prepared.
- The crystallization peak temperature of the amorphous powder prepared by the sol-gel route was found to be nearly 690 °C, as determined by the DSC/TGA experiment at a heating rate of 10 °C/min.
- Using the Kissinger's equation, the activation energy for ZrTiO₄ crystallization was determined to be 850 kJ/mol.
- Calcination at 550 °C for 1 h developed ZrTiO₄ nanocrystals of 15 nm in size determined by XRD. In addition, high crystallinity and particle growth were confirmed by TEM studies.

Acknowledgements

This report is based upon work supported by National Science Foundation (NSF) under grant no. 0933763.

References

[1] L. Pandolfi, S. Kaciulis, G. Padeletti, A. Cusma, M. Viticoli, Deposition and characterization of ZrTiO₄ thin films, *Surf. Interf. Anal.* 36 (2004) 1159-1162.

This is the accepted manuscript (postprint) of the following article:

E. Salahinejad, M. Hadianfard, D. Macdonald, I. Karimi, D. Vashae, L. Tayebi, *Aqueous sol-gel synthesis of zirconium titanate (ZrTiO₄) nanoparticles using chloride precursors*, *Ceramics International*, 38 (2012) 6145-6149.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2012.04.064>

- [2] M.Z.C. Hu, E.A. Payzant, K.R. Booth, C.J. Rawn, R.D. Hunt, L.F. Allard, Ultrafine microsphere particles of zirconium titanate produced by homogeneous dielectric-tuning coprecipitation, *J. Mater. Sci.* 38 (2003) 3831-3844.
- [3] I.C. Cosentino, E. N. S. Muccillo, R. Muccillo, Development of zirconia-titania porous ceramics for humidity sensors. *Sens. Actuators B* 96 (2003) 677-683.
- [4] J.L. Lakshmi, N.J. Ihasz, J.M. Miller, Synthesis, characterization and ethanol partial oxidation studies of V₂O₅ catalysts supported on TiO₂-SiO₂ and TiO₂-ZrO₂ sol-gel mixed oxides, *J. Mol. Catal. Chem.* 165 (2001) 199-209.
- [5] M.E. Zorn, D.T. Tompkins, W.A. Zeltner, M.A. Anderson, Photocatalytic oxidation of acetone vapor on TiO₂/ZrO₂ thin films, *Appl. Catal. B* 23 (1999) 1-8.
- [6] D.V. Shtansky, M.I. Petrzhik, I.A. Bashkova, F.V. Kiryukhantsev-Korneev, A.N. Sheveiko, E.A. Levashov, Adhesion, friction, and deformation characteristics of Ti-(Ca,Zr)-(C,N,O,P) coatings for orthopedic and dental implants, *Phys. Solid State* 48 (2006) 1301-1308.
- [7] L.Y. Zhu, D. Xu, G. Yu, X.Q. Wang, Preparation and characterization of zirconium titanate fibers with good high temperature performance, *J. Sol-Gel Sci. Technol.* 49 (2009) 341-346.
- [8] J. Macan, A. Gajovi, H. Ivankovic, Porous zirconium titanate ceramics synthesized by sol-gel process, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 29 (2009) 691-696.
- [9] L. G. Karakchiev, T. M. Zima, and N. Z. Lyakhov, Low-temperature synthesis of zirconium titanate, *Inorg. Mater.* 37 (2001) 386-390.

This is the accepted manuscript (postprint) of the following article:

E. Salahinejad, M. Hadianfard, D. Macdonald, I. Karimi, D. Vashae, L. Tayebi, *Aqueous sol-gel synthesis of zirconium titanate (ZrTiO₄) nanoparticles using chloride precursors*, *Ceramics International*, 38 (2012) 6145-6149.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2012.04.064>

[10] M. Anarianainarivelo, R. J.P. Corriu, D. Leclercq, P. H. Mutin, A. Vioux, Nonhydrolytic sol-gel process: aluminium and zirconium titanate gels, *J. Sol-Gel Sci. Technol.* 8 (1997) 89–93.

[11] M. Anarianainarivelo, R. J.P. Corriu, D. Leclercq, P. H. Mutin, A. Vioux. Non-hydrolytic sol-gel process: zirconium titanate gels, *J. Mater. Chem.* 7 (1997) 279–284.

[12] Lu, Q. F., Chen, D. R. and Jiao, X. L., Synthesis of long ZrTiO₄ fibers by a sol-gel process free of organic components. *J. Mater. Chem.* 13 (2003) 1127–1131.

[13] S. X. Zhang, J. B. Li, J. Cao, H. Z. Zhaim, B. Zhang, Preparation, microstructure and microwave dielectric properties of Zr_xTi_{1-x}O₄ (x = 0.40–0.60) ceramics, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 21 (2001) 2931–2936.

[14] S. Naci Koc, Zirconium titanate synthesis by diethanol amine based sol-gel route, *J. Sol-Gel Sci. Technol.* 38 (2006) 277–281.

[15] M. C. Barrera, M. Viniegra, J. Escobar, M. Vrinat, J. A. de los Reyes, F. Murrieta, J. García, Highly active MoS₂ on wide-pore ZrO₂-TiO₂ mixed oxides. *Catal. Today* 98 (2004) 131–139.

[16] E. L. Sham, M. A. G.Aranda, E. M. Farfan-Torres, J. C. Gottifredi, M. Martínez-Lara, S. Bruque, Zirconium titanate from sol-gel synthesis-thermal decomposition and quantitative phase analysis. *J. Solid State Chem.* 139 (1998) 225–232.

[17] M.R. Mohammadi, D.J. Fray, Synthesis and characterisation of nanosized TiO₂-ZrO₂ binary system prepared by an aqueous sol-gel process: Physical and sensing properties, *Sens. Actuators, B* 155 (2011) 568–576.

[18] H.E. Kissinger, Reaction kinetics in differential thermal analysis, *Anal. Chem.* 29 (1957) 1702–1706.

This is the accepted manuscript (postprint) of the following article:

E. Salahinejad, M. Hadianfard, D. Macdonald, I. Karimi, D. Vashae, L. Tayebi, *Aqueous sol-gel synthesis of zirconium titanate (ZrTiO₄) nanoparticles using chloride precursors*, *Ceramics International*, 38 (2012) 6145-6149.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2012.04.064>

- [19] M. Macias, P.J. Sanchez-Soto, J.A. Navio, Kinetic study of crystallization in zirconium titanate from an amorphous reactive prepared precursor, *J. Non-Cryst. Solids* 147-148 (1992) 262-265.
- [20] H.R. Wang, Y.L. Gao, G.H. Min, X.D. Hui, Y.F. Ye, Primary crystallization in rapidly solidified Zr₇₀Cu₂₀Ni₁₀ alloy from a supercooled liquid region, *Phys. Lett. A* 314 (2003) 81-87.
- [21] H. P. Klug, L. E. Alexander, *X-ray Diffraction Procedures*. J. Wiley, New York, 1974.
- [22] J. A. Navio, F. J. Marchena, M. Macias, P. J. Sanchez-Soto, P. Pichat, Formation of zirconium titanate powder from a sol-gel prepared reactive precursor, *J. Mater. Sci.* 27 (1992) 2463-2467.
- [23] Y. Park, Y. H. Kim, H. G. Kim, The phase transition and microwave dielectric properties of tin modified zirconium titanate by melting process, *Mater. Sci. Eng. B* 40 (1996) 37-41.
- [24] A. E. McHale, R. S. Roth, Low-temperature phase relationships in the system ZrO₂-TiO₂. *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 69 (1986) 827-832.
- [25] A. Gajovic, K. Furic, S. Music, I. Djerdj, A. Tonejc, A. M. Tonejc, D. S. Su, R. Schlögl, Mechanism of ZrTiO₄ synthesis by mechanochemical processing of TiO₂ and ZrO₂. *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 89 (2006) 2196-2205.
- [26] A. Gajovic, I. Djerdj, K. Furic, R. Schlögl, D. S. Su, Preparation of nanostructured ZrTiO₄ by solid state reaction in equimolar mixture of TiO₂ and ZrO₂. *Cryst. Res. Technol.* 41 (2006) 1076-1081.

This is the accepted manuscript (postprint) of the following article:

E. Salahinejad, M. Hadianfard, D. Macdonald, I. Karimi, D. Vashae, L. Tayebi, *Aqueous sol-gel synthesis of zirconium titanate (ZrTiO₄) nanoparticles using chloride precursors*, *Ceramics International*, 38 (2012) 6145-6149.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2012.04.064>

- [27] M. Stubicar, V. Bermanec, N. Stubicar, D. Kudrnovski, D. Krumes, Microstructure evolution of an equimolar powder mixture of ZrO₂-TiO₂ during high-energy ball-milling and post-annealing, *J. Alloys Compd.* 316 (2001) 316-320.
- [28] L. Bonhomme-Coury, N. Lequeux, S. Mussotte, P. Bloch, Preparation of Al₂TiO₅-ZrO₂ mixed powders via sol-gel process, *J. Sol-Gel Sci. Tech.* 2 (1994) 371-.
- [29] H.A.J. Thomas, R. Steven, and E. Gilbert, Effect of zirconia additions on the reaction sintering of aluminium titanate, *J. Mater. Sci.* 26 (1991) 3613-3616.
- [30] M. Macias, P.J. Sanchez-Soto, J.A. Navio, Kinetic study of crystallization in zirconium titanate from an amorphous reactive prepared precursor, *J. Non-Cryst. Solids* 147-148 (1992) 262.
- [31] I. Zhitomirsky, L. Gal-Or, S. Klein, Electrolytic deposition of ZrTiO₄ films, *J. Mater. Sci. Lett.* 14 (1995) 60-62.
- [32] H. Wei, R. Wang, J. Zhao, J. Bud, R. Wang, Z. Wang, L. Yu, Y. Wei, Synthesis of ZrTiO₄ and MgAl₂O₄ powders via non-hydrolytic sol-gel route using alcohol as oxygen donor, *Adv. Mater. Res.* 284-286 (2011) 1471-1474.

This is the accepted manuscript (postprint) of the following article:

E. Salahinejad, M. Hadianfard, D. Macdonald, I. Karimi, D. Vashae, L. Tayebi, *Aqueous sol-gel synthesis of zirconium titanate ($ZrTiO_4$) nanoparticles using chloride precursors*, *Ceramics International*, 38 (2012) 6145-6149.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2012.04.064>

Figures

Fig. 1. TEM micrograph of the xerogel powder particles showing agglomeration (a), that showing nanoparticles of 5 nm in size (b), and the related SAD pattern suggesting an amorphous phase (c).

This is the accepted manuscript (postprint) of the following article:

E. Salahinejad, M. Hadianfard, D. Macdonald, I. Karimi, D. Vashaei, L. Tayebi, *Aqueous sol-gel synthesis of zirconium titanate (ZrTiO₄) nanoparticles using chloride precursors*, *Ceramics International*, 38 (2012) 6145-6149.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2012.04.064>

Fig. 2. TGA and DSC profiles of the xerogel at a heating rate of 10 °C/min.

Fig. 3. DSC curves of ZrTiO₄ crystallization obtained at the different heating rates (a) and

Kissinger plot for ZrTiO₄ crystallization (b).

This is the accepted manuscript (postprint) of the following article:

E. Salahinejad, M. Hadianfard, D. Macdonald, I. Karimi, D. Vashae, L. Tayebi, *Aqueous sol-gel synthesis of zirconium titanate ($ZrTiO_4$) nanoparticles using chloride precursors*, *Ceramics International*, 38 (2012) 6145-6149.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2012.04.064>

Fig. 4. XRD pattern of the xerogel (a) and the powders calcined at 500 (b), 550 (c), and 600 (d) °C.

This is the accepted manuscript (postprint) of the following article:

E. Salahinejad, M. Hadianfard, D. Macdonald, I. Karimi, D. Vashae, L. Tayebi, *Aqueous sol-gel synthesis of zirconium titanate ($ZrTiO_4$) nanoparticles using chloride precursors*, *Ceramics International*, 38 (2012) 6145-6149.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2012.04.064>

Fig. 5. TEM micrograph (a) and SAD pattern (b) of the powder specimen calcined at 600 °C.